
MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSES (MOOCs) IN INDIA: A GOLDEN CHANCE FOR TEACHERS, STUDENTS AND EDUCATORS

Mrs. Rupali Sham Bhosale

Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author - Mrs. Rupali Sham Bhosale

Email- bhosalerupali90@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are a platform for online learning courses. The paper discussed on MOOCs platforms available on various countries and usually government and non-government platforms. Indian government takes to the initiative create its own MOOCs platform in the year 2016, the Ministry of Education develops Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM). Teachers, students, and educators have a golden chance to develop communication skills, new methods for classroom teaching, update knowledge, and take extra knowledge for skill development, etc. through MOOCs platforms. The Government of India takes initiative to create the Annual Refresher Programme in Teaching (ARPIT) under Pandit Madan Mohan Malviya National Mission on Teachers and Teaching (PMMNMTT) and has arranged an online Faculty Development Programme (FDP). Anyone can take any course on any platform those who are interested join SWAYAM platforms and also other international platforms to complete any courses.

Keywords: MOOC, SWAYAM, MOOCs in India, SWAYAM co-coordinator, Teachers, FDP.

Introduction:

The traditional education system is now changing and online learning and online platforms comes to change their education system because they update learners' knowledge. The teachers and students were not updating their knowledge in traditional education. Now, MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) platforms create online courses and make tremendous positive changes in education system. MOOCs is an international concept of online learning and anyone, anytime, and anywhere users enrolling in platform courses and also completing them. The teachers are aware of that concept because an online course has

updated their knowledge and teachers provide it to students. The use of technology in the classroom offers a global development for learning that allows accessibility anytime, anywhere, and with other users, students can access the source material without considering any geographic limits.

Private companies create online courses and establish their online platform other side various countries take initiative to create government online course platforms for anyone can join or complete their courses.

Overview of MOOC Platform:

Students and teachers worldwide have access to the best courses from the best universities opening up the classroom edX's MOOCs, The edX platform was developed to enable educators to provide education at a scale that is of equal or higher quality than on-campus instruction.

Globally companies create their private own MOOCs platforms Udemy, Coursera, Miriadax, Microsoft, Canvas Network, Datacamp, Udacity, Treehouse, OpenSAP, Kadenze, free Codecamp, The great course plus, Master class, CodeCademy, iversity, Edureka, Open education by blackboard courses, Qwiklabs, MIT open courseware, Gacco, Federica, Rwaq, OpenHPI, Skillshop, Hubspot Academy, Polimi open knowledge, Brilliant, EMMA, NovoEd, Stanford open edx, Test Automation University, Desire2Learn, OpenLearning, World Science U, Stepik, Scrimba, Open classrooms, mongoDB University, IndonesiAx, Acumen academy, Complexity explorer, MOOC ED, Semrush academy, Kaggle, MRUniversity, Sadie valeri atelier, JuliaAcademy, Jovian, The Odin project, LinkedIn Learning, Skill share, Youtube, Pluralsight, edx, AWS skill builder, FutureLearn, Domestika, Creative live, Openup Ed platform, etc. further governments also create MOOCs platforms in this FunMOOC, Independent, ThaiMOOC, Eduopen, Open 2 study, Edraak, Open edx, SWAYAM, etc.

Anyone can join any platform and complete any course. Some courses are freely available on that platform and have no examination fee and many more courses have free-of-cost education but they take only an examination fee. All platforms provide education with audio-video education materials, PDF text, and also provide a discussion forum for discussing any quires related that courses.

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MOOCs in India:

For students, teachers, educators, and anyone else interested in online learning, MOOC platforms create a variety of nations. India has similarly taken the initiative in developing its own MOOC platform. The SWAYAM, which usually stands for "Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds," is an Indian MOOCs platform that was introduced in 2016 as part of the Digital India programme by the Ministry of Education, Government of India. The SWAYAM has been charged with providing students with the best learning opportunities through the development of high-quality content under the supervision of nine national coordinators. The following table shows the nine coordinators and their working sectors, such as elated problems and other areas of expertise. The nine coordinators have fixed departments for the design of courses.

Table No. 1

SWAYAM coordinates and working sectors

Department of working sectors	SWAYAM nine coordinates
Post-graduate Education	NPTEL
	AICTE
	IIMB
	UGC
Under-Graduate Education	NPTEL
	AICTE
	CEC
	IIMB
Out of School Education	IGNOG
	NITTTR
School Education	NIOS
	NCERT

Students at universities choose the courses they are interested in taking, accomplish them with an exam certificate, and then the course credits are immediately added to their academic year's result sheet. According to the new education policy, it is required that students register on the SWAYAM platform, complete at least one course, and receive course certificates. The dissemination of course materials takes place across 4, 6, 8, 12, 15, and 24 weeks. The SWAYAM courses are free to take, however, whether you need to take an examination subsequent, there is a significant cost. Students take any course to elevate their communication and interpersonal skills, update their knowledge, gain experience with online learning, turn in assignments, participate in discussion forums, solve any issues relating to the course, etc.

NPTEL and AICTE launch a faculty development project. They develop faculty development courses (FDP) to advance their careers and broaden their topic knowledge. After taking the required courses and tests, the majority of the faculty members applied for an FDP certificate. NPTEL advised that colleges and universities require faculty members to enroll in at least one NPTEL course every semester, whether it is in their field of study or another. This will guarantee ongoing education and updating of aerodynamics, provide perspective further into pedagogical approaches of the course, generate suggestions for various approaches to curriculum implementation, etc.

Additionally, NPTEL offers courses on employing technologies in the classroom, learner-centered teaching techniques, intellectual property, copyright law the educational system, etc. To help

fresh teacher hires grasp the process, this may be suggested.

The Government of India under the Ministry of Human Resource Development in the year of 2018 has launched Annual Refresher Programme in Teaching (ARPIT) and arrange online FDP courses through National Resource Centres (NRCs) under Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya National Mission on Teachers and Teaching (PMMMNMIT). The online FDP courses create awareness among faculty members of the recent development of the discipline and new and emerging trends in particular subjects through technology-based online refresher courses. The FDP course platforms have increased the best of teachers' and teachers' knowledge, problem-solving platform, recent research knowledge, and motivation for creating some new research and new patents in their field.

Merits of Online Courses:

The online course platforms increase learners' knowledge and update users' profiles for acquiring new jobs and developing skills. Teachers have updated their knowledge through that platform and note down that concept and used it in their classroom because students are updating their knowledge and growing our nation fast. Globally our nation has in developing countries that why we have to develop or increase our knowledge.

SWAYAM platform enhances the skills, knowledge, communication, benefits of career development, extra achievements in our field, specialization of a particular course or subject, etc. In rural and urban areas students also involve swayam platform to develop imagination power and enhance their thinking level. Learners are enrolled in more than several courses and several platforms at one time.

1. The providers offer adaptable and reasonably priced educational possibilities that students at all levels can take advantage of to succeed in a society that is becoming more difficult, complicated, and technologically advanced.
2. MOOCs platforms provide free-of-cost registration and course completion but if you want certification you have to pay that exam fee. SWAYAM has taken initiative for anyone, wherever, and at any time can enroll in courses and complete the courses for free.
3. Teachers enjoy the benefits of sharing information with a vast number of teachers but it also poses a challenge to them for the upgradation of their skills.
4. Teachers after completing MOOCs courses can apply for other skillful jobs and improve their teaching methods further; they use also course content or information for teaching and give updated knowledge to classroom students.
5. In that SWAYAM platform teachers complete MOOC courses because courses are available in regional languages that's why teachers learn so many things and implementation in their work.
6. Teachers can get communication experience with other teachers and professionals they can solve any problems with their communication and also improve their communication.
7. Deliberation about professional careers with strangers on the internet helped teachers increase their self-assurance.
8. Teachers have a fantastic opportunity to develop their textual skills by learning to absorb more content faster, which they view as a crucial skill in the digital world as well as to come up with effective lesson planning strategies.
9. MOOCs provide both learners and teachers the chance to advance their education, expand their skill sets, and change their lives.
10. The SWAYAM provides a facility for credit transfer courses, students complete one course in one semester and add their marks to their degree certificates.
11. Teachers and students are engaging courses with their interests and increase self-motivation for course completion add their points in results and update profile.

Conclusion:

The MOOC platforms develop courses so that anyone can complete them, build their abilities, and address any inadequacies. Such courses are usually completed by teachers, who then use what they have learned in their offline teaching for efficient communication between them and their pupils. Teachers can educate their pupils about MOOC platforms by becoming familiar with them. When teachers are delivering, they may also make references to a specific online learning environment, directing students there to enroll in a course and advance their understanding of the material. They can take an exam, pay the required minimum costs, pass it, and then apply for a certificate if they desire certification in a specific field of study or course. The credential will be used by the students to build a good resume and find new employment opportunities.

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